

Online Augmentation for Presentation Attack Detection on ID Cards

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Abstract: This work proposes a Presentation of Attack Detection (PAD) on ID card systems, focusing on improving the detection of manual composite attacks. These kinds of attacks are used in a remote verification system to impersonate the identity of one subject in order to obtain benefits. For this purpose, relevant text can be modified, copied, and pasted. Faces and other areas can be manually changed because of the alignment of the originally issued ID card to a fake ID card. This work proposed an “online” methodology to create composite attack images during the training process and shows that using automatic composite attacks may reduce the error rate in the PAD system. To demonstrate it, three experiments were set up that compared the performance of models trained with and without the aforementioned technique on a private dataset and a cross-evaluation dataset.

Keywords: Biometric, Tampering, PAD, ID Cards.

1 Introduction

Digital remote onboarding has become common in recent years, led by the expansion of online services and transactions [SJ18; SJ19]. Global events, which require remote interactions, have accelerated this trend. Thus, reliance on identification documents, such as ID cards, has become key to safe online interactions. However, this growing usage also creates issues, such as ensuring the integrity and authenticity of remotely presented documents.

A remote verification system comprises two parts. The first one is focused on deciding whether the person in front of the device is physically present, or “live”. The second one focuses on detecting whether the ID card presented by the subject is original, which means discarding any form of modified or falsely presented document. This phase is known as Presentation Attack Detection (PAD), and it typically involves detecting situations such as a document being printed on paper, presented as a photo on a screen, or presenting an original document with modified fields, such as a photo or parts of the text. These attacks are known as “Print”, “Screen” and “Composite” respectively

The “Composite” attack is challenging since it is created manually by the attacker. Training a reliable PAD System means generating hundreds or thousands of images. Detecting

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these attacks—ranging from simple to sophisticated manipulations—has become crucial to prevent online identity fraud. Manual generation methods are slow and error-prone, making them unsuitable for scalable digital onboarding. To address this, we propose an online method for generating diverse composite attacks during training to enhance PAD systems’ generalization.

This work presents the following contributions:

- *Automatic generation*: we introduce six composite attack modalities generated online, demonstrating their relevance for real-world PAD scenarios.
- *End-to-end*: a complete PAD system was developed and evaluated using two convolutional neural networks.
- *Generalization*: intra and cross-database evaluations highlight the system’s generalization and reproducibility using an open-access test set.

The rest of the article is organized as follows: Section 2 summarizes the related works on PAD based on composite images. Section 3 describes and depicts examples of composite images as well as new methods for generating composite images. The experiments and results of this work are then presented in Section 4. We conclude the article in Section 5.

2 Related work

Some publications have explored PAD on ID cards [Be23; GT25; GVT21], focusing mainly on Composite, Printed, and Screen attacks. Composite attacks involve manually or digitally replacing elements (e.g., photo, ID number) on a printed ID using handmade physical elements or image editing. Though effective, this process is time-consuming and poses challenges for accurate document verification.

Only a few open-set datasets exist, e.g.: MIDV-500 [ABC18], MIDV-2020 [Bu21], DLC-2021 [Po22], MIDV-Holo [Ko23], and KID34K [Pa23]. These datasets often include a limited number of subjects but a broad range of attacks. In contrast, private datasets with a larger number of subjects and varied samples tend to yield more robust results.

Stokkenes et al. [SRB18] proposed a banking authentication system using face-based Bloom filters, but did not address composite images.

Similarly, Mudgalgundurao et al. [Mu22] used pixel-wise supervision with DenseNet to detect fake German ID cards by analyzing fine artifacts and patterns, but excluding composite attacks.

Gonzalez et al. [GVT21] introduced a two-stage PAD system with a “Composite” stage targeting identity-swapped images, where facial regions are replaced but text remains unchanged. An improved version added synthetic and plastic card attacks [GT25].

Benalcazar and Tapia [Be23] proposed generating synthetic attack samples using GANs and templates on Chilean ID cards. They created composite bona fide IDs by manually cutting and pasting elements and simulated this process digitally.

Markham et al. [Ma24] evaluated whether adding synthetic attack samples to training improves PAD performance on open-source video datasets. They tested “Print” and “Screen” scenarios but excluded composite attacks.

Finally, Park [Pa23] introduced the KID34K dataset for online fraud detection, including 34,662 images with print and screen attacks across 82 ID cards. No composite attacks were included.

Motivated by previous work, we have identified and explored the challenges posed by composite attacks, both manually and automatically created in a remote ID card verification context, and developed a deep-learning approach based on a composite detector. It is essential to highlight that traditional data augmentation tools do not cover this kind of composite attack for ID cards.

Fig. 1: Illustration of our proposed “online” composite attacks method. The red color illustrates the area that has changed or been swapped.

3 Method

This section presents the datasets used in the experiments, describes how the digital automatic attacks were created, outlines the neural network architectures employed, details the data augmentation configuration, and explains the metrics used for evaluation. Our proposed attack building method is depicted in Figure 1.

3.1 Datasets

This work used three datasets to develop and evaluate a composite PAD system: a private dataset and two open-access datasets. The private dataset was provided by a company only for research purposes, while the two public datasets, MIDV-Holo and DLC-2021, are available in state-of-the-art form. The datasets are described as follows:

3.1.1 Private Dataset

The private dataset comprises bona fide images of ICAO-compliant Chilean ID cards (Figure 2a), along with samples from Spain, Colombia, Ecuador, and Argentina, making a total of 84,689 images. Due to privacy restrictions, the dataset is not publicly available. However, the readers can request an evaluation of external models. It includes several types of manually created composite attacks:

- **Portrait Substitution (PS):** The face area is replaced with that of another individual, using various shapes (e.g., rectangular, oval) as shown in Figure 2e.
- **Digital Template (DT):** Fake ID cards are created by editing templates with synthetic faces and false data (Figure 2f, left).
- **Recaptured Template (RT):** Digitally edited templates are printed on plastic (PVC) cards and recaptured (Figure 2f, right).

Fig. 2: Examples of different images used as bona fide and composite attacks for Chilean and Spanish ID cards. A black tag was used in order to protect the identity of the ID card’s owner. Spain’s examples do not include a black tag because they contain random information.

3.1.2 DLC-2021

DLC-2021 dataset includes 10 types of ID documents (cards and passports), originating from those in MIDV-2020. It features video captures of color-laminated mock IDs, unlaminated color, grayscale copies, and screen recaptures, recorded using iPhone XR and Samsung S10 smartphones with wide-angle cameras. For this work, only bona fide samples from four ID cards (Albania, Spain, Estonia, and Slovakia) were used to generate digital composite attacks. Since the attacks provided by this database do not match “Composite” attacks, which is the focus of this article, all original attack samples in the dataset were excluded.

3.1.3 MIDVHolo

This dataset contains five types of documents: “Genuine” documents, which are artificial documents of the country “Utopia”, and four more groups of different attacks performed over the “Original” documents. For this work, only the subset of images contained in the photo_replacement folder, where the “Genuine” documents have their photos replaced, met our needs for testing purposes; therefore, only this subset was used.

3.2 Online image generation

To complement previously described attacks, an “online” system was developed to generate digital composite attacks from bona fide samples, creating potential manipulations not present in existing datasets. These attacks are categorized by the altered document area:

- PS: Bounding boxes of each ID card’s portrait are swapped. These faces were detected by a face detector based on RetinaFace [De20].
- TS: Bounding boxes of text fields of each ID card are swapped at random, regardless of the content of that field. These fields were detected by an in-house text detector [LWS23].
- MS: A patch with a random location and size is selected in both documents and then swapped. This patch can include any area of interest, such as texts, portraits, signatures, or any combination.

Digital generation allows variable cutout shapes (rectangular, oval, polygonal) and two quality levels: basic and seamless. Attacks were generated from bona fide samples in both the private and DLC-2021 datasets (See Figures 2b, 2c, and 2d in Figure 2). All bona fide samples used are genuine ID cards.

Class	Composite Attacks	Training	Validation	Testing
0	Bona fide	61,761	21,827	1,101
1	Manual portrait composite	7,725	2,730	4,000
	Automatic portrait composite	7,725*	2,730	4,000
2	Automatic text substitution	15,450*	5,460	4,000
3	Automatic mixed composite	15,450*	5,460	2,000
4	Digital template	7,725	2,157	173
	Recaptured template	7,725	2,325	2,524

Tab. 1: Summary of the private dataset for the exp-1.(*)Numbers of images in one single epoch.

Digital attacks were generated online during training, allowing for dynamic data augmentation with minimal impact on performance. The main technique used for generating such attacks was the Splicing method, which transfers an area from one image to another.

Each attack type follows a distinct procedure. In Portrait Substitution (PS), facial bounding boxes are detected using RetinaFace [De20] and swapped between images. Text Substitution (TS) uses a CRNN-based text detector [LWS23] to locate and replace text field regions.

Mixed Substitution (MS) randomly selects and exchanges image patches that may contain a mix of elements such as text, portraits, or signatures. Furthermore, post-processing techniques are applied to enhance realism. These include seamless cloning for smooth blending, ellipse masking for gradual transitions, and irregular octagon masking to create more natural-looking patch boundaries.

During training, a number of online attacks are randomly produced from the bona fide samples following the diagram shown in Figure 1. Thus, on each epoch, the model sees all the available images plus a set of randomly produced online digital attacks. For validation, the same strategy is followed, although the set used during the first validation is maintained for the following epochs in order to avoid variance in validation metrics due to newly produced online attacks. The size of each split is shown in Table 1 for reference.

3.3 Metrics

The detection performance of biometric PAD algorithms is standardized in ISO/IEC 30107-3³. The most important metrics for this study are Attack Presentation Classification Error Rate (*APCER*), Bona fide Presentation Classification Error Rate (*BPCER*), and *BPCER_{AP}*. These metrics are key to understanding the performance of a PAD algorithm.

APCER indicates the proportion of attack presentations misclassified as bona fide. As shown in Equation 1, N_{PAIS} is the number of attack images, and RES_i is 1 if the i th image is correctly classified as an attack, or 0 otherwise.

$$APCER_{PAIS} = 1 - \frac{1}{N_{PAIS}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{PAIS}} RES_i \quad (1) \quad BPCER = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{BF}} RES_i}{N_{BF}} \quad (2)$$

In contrast, *BPCER* represents the proportion of bona fide samples incorrectly classified as attacks. It is computed as shown in Equation 2. Here, N_{BF} is the number of bona fide images, and RES_i follows the same definition as above. *APCER* and *BPCER* assess system performance at a given operating point.

BPCER_{AP} and Equal Error Rate (*EER*) help evaluate performance at specific thresholds. *EER* is the point where *APCER* equals *BPCER*, corresponding to the diagonal intersection in a Detection Error Trade-off (DET) curve. *BPCER_{AP}* is simply defined as the *BPCER* metric obtained when calibrating the system threshold at a point where the *APCER* metric matches $100/AP$. For our work, *BPCER₁₀*, *BPCER₂₀* and *BPCER₁₀₀* were evaluated, which correspond to *APCER* values of 10%, 5% and 1% respectively.

4 Experiment and Results

This section details the experiments carried out to study the impact of automatic and manual composite ID cards, their configuration and details, and the results obtained.

³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/79520.html>

4.1 Experiment 1: Baseline

The main objective of this first experiment is to select a baseline model and configuration for a composite PAD system. This experiment used the private dataset for training, validation, and testing (See Table 1 for more details). An initial exploratory analysis was performed, where multiple architectures and different configurations were evaluated.

For this work, two neural networks with different architectures, EfficientNetv2-B2 and MobileViTv2-175, have been selected. Both architectures are small CNNs (<15M parameters). First, EfficientNetv2-B2 model [TL21] was developed using a Neural Architecture Search (NAS) to optimize model size and training speed jointly. This way, an improved progressive learning method adaptively adjusts regularization along with image size. The EfficientNetv2-B2 has 10.1M parameters, and performs 1.7G FLOPS.

On the other hand, MobileViTv2-175 architecture [MR23] is a hybrid network that combines the strengths of CNNs and Vision Transformers. This model has 14.3M parameters, and performs 5.52G FLOPS. Both EfficientNetv2-B2 and MobileViTv2-175 were initialized with ImageNet1k weights⁴.

Both models were trained as a 5-class classification: bona fide, portrait-substitution (manual + automatic), text-substitution, mixed-substitution, and digital/recaptured templates. Training used a batch size of 64, the categorical cross-entropy loss function, a learning rate of $5e^{-4}$ with cosine decay, and the AdamW optimizer with $1e^{-5}$ weight decay. Early stopping with a patience of 15 epochs was applied. Both were trained on an NVIDIA-A100 GPU. During training, several classic augmentation techniques, such as random vertical and horizontal flips, grayscale, brightness, and contrast, were also applied.

Architecture		Portrait	Text	Mixed	Templates
EfficientNetv2-B2	<i>EER</i>	2.62	3.27	5.83	6.53
	<i>BPCER</i> ₁₀	0.09	0.09	2.00	3.81
	<i>BPCER</i> ₂₀	0.45	1.00	9.08	8.54
	<i>BPCER</i> ₁₀₀	11.35	36.78	41.42	25.52
MobileViTv2-175	<i>EER</i>	1.73	2.38	4.55	4.90
	<i>BPCER</i> ₁₀	0.09	0.09	0.73	2.54
	<i>BPCER</i> ₂₀	0.36	0.36	3.54	4.90
	<i>BPCER</i> ₁₀₀	4.72	21.89	26.70	10.81

Tab. 2: Exp-1. Summary results of EfficientNetv2-B2 vs MobileViTv2-175. All the values are in %.

Table 2, shows the results comparison between both networks segregated by Portrait, Text, and Templates composite attacks. *EER* is reported along with three operational points: *BPCER*₁₀, *BPCER*₂₀, and *BPCER*₁₀₀. It is essential to highlight that the operational point selected depends on application requirements. According to the results of both networks, MobileViTv2-175 clearly achieved the best results in every type of attack. After this analysis,

⁴ https://github.com/leondgarse/keras_cv_attention_models?tab=readme-ov-file#mobilevit_v2

MobileViTv2-175 network was selected as a baseline to understand the contributions and performance of manual composite attacks in relation to automatic composite attacks.

Fig. 3: Experiment 1. Left: DET curve for MobileViTv2-175 (Best model). Right: DET curve for EfficientNetv2-B2. The black line represents binary results (bona fide vs all the attacks).

The DET curve for comparison of different thresholds is reported in Figure 3. In these plots, we can see the performance of the models broken down into different types of attacks. Thus, we can identify the most difficult types of composite attacks for the model. All the curves are presented for EfficientNetv2-B2 and MobileViTv2-175. The “Templates” attack is identified as the most difficult in both cases with a high EER . On the other hand, the “Portrait substitution” has the lowest EER .

4.2 Experiment 2: Manual vs digital attacks

Our next goal was to evaluate whether adding digital attacks improves the performance of physical manipulations. To do so, we proposed a new experiment in which the testing set would be composed only of bona fide and physical attack images. This was done by excluding any digital manipulation or template from the testing set used in the previous experiment. To evaluate this theory, we compared the following models:

- Model-0: MobileViTv2-175 from section 4.1, which was trained with *manual and automatic* composite and templates.
- Model-1: MobileViTv2-175 trained only with *manual* composite and templates.
- Model-2: MobileViTv2-175 trained only with *automatic* composite and templates.

Manual portrait composite-MobileViTv2-175			
	Model-0	Model-1	Model-2
<i>EER</i>	1.72	4.52	4.65
<i>BPCER</i> ₁₀	0.09	1.09	1.18
<i>BPCER</i> ₂₀	0.36	3.81	4.27
<i>BPCER</i> ₁₀₀	2.72	16.17	21.07

Tab. 3: Exp-2. Summary results of MobileViTv2-175 for the three models. All the values are in %.

Fig. 4: Experiment 2. DET curves for each of the models described in Section 4.2

Table 3 shows the results of the manual portrait attacks for the different MobileViTv2-175s (Model-0, Model-1, and Model-2). On Figure 4 it can be observed that Model-2 has very similar metrics to Model-1, and using both types of attacks in training yields the best results with Model-0. These results show that creating automatic composite attack images to compensate for the dataset’s lack of manual composite images significantly improves detection.

4.3 Experiment 3: Cross-dataset evaluation

To validate our methodology using an externally generated set of documents, a cross-dataset has been created based on the three datasets mentioned in Section 3.1. For experiments 1 and 2, the bona fide group consists of images of bona fide documents, whereas the open-sets, such as DLC-2021 and MIDV-Holo, contain bona fide images that are PVC-printed.

Attacks	Count	Attacks	Metric	Private-set	Cross-set
Bona fide	1,101	Manual portrait composite	<i>EER</i>	1.72	11.56
Automatic portrait composite	32,000		<i>BPCER</i> ₁₀	0.09	4.30
Manual portrait composite	4,427		<i>BPCER</i> ₂₀	0.36	6.90
			<i>BPCER</i> ₁₀₀	2.72	11.70
		Automatic portrait composite	<i>EER</i>	2.01	1.50
			<i>BPCER</i> ₁₀	0.01	0.10
			<i>BPCER</i> ₂₀	0.09	0.20
			<i>BPCER</i> ₁₀₀	11.99	2.50

Tab. 4: Summary of cross-set dataset.

Tab. 5: Private vs open-set datasets. Values are in %.

To evaluate in a realistic scenario, the bona fide images used belong to the testing sets used in experiments 1 and 2. Meanwhile, the composite attacks belong to the DLC-2021 and MIDV-Holo databases. The composition of the resulting set is shown in Table 4.

Table 5 shows the comparison results of evaluating Model-0 over the testing split of our private and the open-set datasets to compare the results with the SOTA.

According to the results shown in Figure 5, the automatic attacks were the easiest to detect in both datasets. On the other hand, manual composite attacks are still a challenge because most do not involve visual artifacts, traces, or noise.

Fig. 5: Experiment 3. Illustrate the DET curves for each of the sets and attacks.

5 Conclusion

This work proposed an “online” methodology for creating and improving composite attack detection based on ID cards on PAD systems, which also complements regular data augmentation. Manual composite attacks are fake ID cards that can be created using open-set resources available. Producing them in huge quantities for training a PAD system is time-consuming and costly. Because of that, using our automatic composite attacks allows us to complement the data the model trains on and thus generalize better than only using manual composite attacks. The results show that the proposed method and the end-to-end PAD are suitable for detecting challenging composite scenarios on intra and cross-datasets.

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